

Precise Sparse Abstract Execution via Cross-Domain Interaction (Artifact)

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1 OVERVIEW

This artifact is for *Precise Sparse Abstract Execution via Cross-Domain Interaction* by Xiao Cheng, Jiawei Wang and Yulei Sui published at ICSE 2024. We believe our artifact deserves both the “Available” and “Reusable” badges. The artifact is publicly available at <https://zenodo.org/records/10461661>. It is packaged as a Docker image and can reproduce the tables in Section 5 (Evaluation) of the paper. The artifact can be reused to analyze customized programs. The source code can also be modified to fit specific needs.

Section 2 of this document provides instructions on setting up the environment and running a quick experiment to verify everything works. Section 3 provides instructions on reproducing our evaluation and varying the experiment through changes to source code, limits, and using new programs for analysis. Specifically, Section 3.1 shows how our artifact supports our claims and Section 3.2 shows how to reuse our artifact.

1.1 Dependencies

This artifact requires Docker (tested with version 20.10.20 on an Ubuntu 20.04 machine) and the initial instructions for loading the image and starting a container assume a UNIX shell. An AMD64/x86-64 machine is also required. As our experiment performs analysis on large programs, a platform with **a minimum of 128 GB’s memory** is required.

1.2 Container Layout

Within the container (Section 2.1), from `/workspace/` directory, the container has the following structure (some directories irrelevant to our purposes are omitted):

```
.
|-- SVF/** # SVF source and build tree.
|-- SAE/** # SAE source and build tree
`-- Reproduce/
    |-- reproduce_all # reproduce RQ1 RQ2 and RQ3
    |-- rq1 # reproduce RQ1
    |-- rq1_file/** # bitcodes used in RQ1
    |-- rq2 # reproduce RQ2
    |-- rq2_file/** # bitcodes used in RQ2
    |-- rq3 # reproduce RQ3
    |-- rq3_file/** # bitcodes used in RQ3
    |-- sae # our tool
    |-- test_baselines # to reproduce test baseline
    |-- test.c # reproduce a simple test
    |-- other
    | |-- telnet-client.bc
    | |-- * (remainder)
    `-- * (remainder)
```

2 GETTING STARTED GUIDE

In this section, we first load the Docker image and run a container, and then perform a simple experiment to verify things work.

2.1 Environment Setup

First, we must pull the Docker image and start a container to run the benchmarks in:

- (1) `$ docker pull icseartifact/sae`
- (2) `$ docker run --rm -dit --name=sae icseartifact/sae bash`
- (3) `$ docker exec -it sae bash`

Now, we are in a Ubuntu container, ready to run experiments. For convenience, some tools like `vim` and `git` are available. All instructions should be performed within this container unless otherwise specified.

2.2 A Simple Test

This section aims to perform a simple test to ascertain the functionality of our tool (called CSA) as well as the baseline tools, including `INFER`, `CPPCHECK`, `IKOS`, `KLEE` and `SPARROW`.

Testing our tool. A precompiled executable has been provided in the folder `/workspace/Reproduce/` for your convenience. To perform a simple test, follow these instructions:

- (1) `$ cd /workspace/Reproduce`
- (2) `$./sae -overflow test.ll`

Our tool will print a buffer overflow bug report on the terminal.

Testing baselines. To test the functionality of our baselines, execute the following commands:

- (1) `$ cd /workspace/Reproduce`
- (2) `$./test_baselines`

Each baseline tool will print its analysis result.

3 STEP-BY-STEP INSTRUCTIONS

This section details how to reproduce our results (Section 3.1) and usage of our tool (Section 3.2).

3.1 Reproducing our Results

You can reproduce all the results in a single script by following Section 3.1.1. For reproducing each result separately, refer to the detailed instructions in Sections 3.1.3-3.1.4.

Note: You may get an overall better result compared to our previously accepted version, as we have further optimized our tool for enhanced performance.

3.1.1 All the Results. To replicate all the results, execute the following commands:

- (1) `$ cd /workspace/Reproduce`

```
(2) $ ./reproduce_all
```

Note: The process may take up to 18 hours, depending on your testing environment, and requires up to 100 GB of memory. All our results will be visualized on the terminal.

3.1.2 *NIST Benchmark (RQ1)*. To reproduce the result on NIST benchmark in Table 3, run these commands:

```
(1) $ cd /workspace/Reproduce
(2) $ ./rq1
```

3.1.3 *Bugs in Real-World Projects (RQ2)*. To reproduce the result running on real-world projects in Table 4, execute these commands:

```
(1) $ cd /workspace/Reproduce
(2) $ ./rq2
```

3.1.4 *Ablation Analysis (RQ3)*. To reproduce the result in Table 5, proceed as follows:

```
(1) $ cd /workspace/Reproduce
(2) $ ./rq3
```

3.2 Usage of our Tool

Customized input. The pre-compiled binary of our tool is located in the `/workspace/Reproduce/` folder. To use the tool, execute the following command in the terminal:

```
$ ./workspace/Reproduce/sae -overflow bitcode_path
```

Here, `bitcode_path` should be replaced with the path to the LLVM bitcode of the program you wish to analyze. Note that the program should be compiled into an LLVM bitcode. We have provided some sample programs in the `/workspace/Reproduce/other/` directory. You can also compile any program of your choice into LLVM bitcode using Whole Program LLVM (<https://github.com/SRI-CSL/gllvm>) to build bitcode by using `gclang` or `gclang++` as the compiler.

Modifying source code. If you need to tailor the tool to your specific needs, follow these steps:

- (1) Modify the source code under `/workspace/SAE/src/`.
- (2) Navigate to the build directory:

```
$ cd /workspace/SAE/Release-build
```
- (3) Run the `cmake` command with the SVF directory specified:

```
$ cmake .. -DSVF_DIR=/workspace/SVF
```
- (4) Compile the source code:

```
$ make -j4
```

Upon successful compilation, the executable will reflect the modifications (`/workspace/SAE/Release-build/bin/sae`). Use the same method as described earlier to run the modified tool.